

**WHAT IS BLENDED LEARNING?
WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF BLENDED LEARNING?**

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Annotation: *This article discusses the concept and characteristics of blended learning, as well as the many consequences, consequences, and future prospects of blended learning in higher education in a world where information and communication technologies (ICTs) are increasingly interconnected reviewed the directions. In terms of effectiveness, the authors argue that access to blended learning is combined around success and students' perception of the learning environment. Success and exit rates for face-to-face and online courses are comparable to mixed education courses because they interact with minority status.*

Key words: *education, blended learning, traditional education, online education, independent learning, hybrid learning, traditional face-to-face learning and online distance learning.*

The subject of upbringing a physically healthy, educated, spiritually mature, mature person has been deeply studied by oriental scholars. It is no coincidence that in the works and theoretical teachings of such great scholars as Aristotle, Ibn Sino, Bakhovuddin Nakshbandi, Najmiddin Kubro, great importance is attached to the development and upbringing of the young. From time immemorial, our intelligent ancestors not only preserved their nationality and spiritual wealth, but also aspired to such noble ideas as goodness, knowledge, enlightenment and independence

Undoubtedly, every nation wants its children to be harmonious. In fact, perfection is a very broad concept. The glossary of our language describes perfection as follows: "physical and mental maturity, maturity, fluffy state of perfection, etc." Life itself requires a teacher who educates such people to have deep knowledge, high moral and ethical qualities, pedagogical skills, to teach science effectively using modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods. This is a requirement of the period.

There are many types of education available to the younger generation. In the age of science and technology, the process of education is developing accordingly. One such type of education is blended learning. Blended education is emerging as one of the most promising learning practices in educational institutions. Blended learning basically combines two learning environments: traditional face-to-face learning and online distance learning.

Therefore, a wide range of opportunities is being created in our country. In particular, there is a growing interest in foreign languages in our country, especially in English.

At a time when the role of blended learning in the global pandemic is becoming increasingly important, it is also important for higher education institutions to teach traditional lessons in conjunction with online lessons in the process of teaching on the basis of credit module education. It is no exaggeration to say that blended learning has become a turning point in modern education.

What is blended learning? What is its essence?

In the research literature, the terms “blended learning”, “hybrid learning”, “technology-mediated learning”, “web-enhanced learning” and “mixed-mode learning” are often interchangeable is applied.

Definition of Blended Learning.

There are many definitions of blended or hybrid learning. Graham defined blended learning systems as a combination of face-to-face with computer-mediated instruction. Ross and Gage differentiated between web and technology-enhanced courses that incorporate online supplementary components within traditional courses without reducing face-to-face time and hybrid courses where in class time is replaced by online course work [1; 2]. Picciano described blended learning as a method of instruction that combines online with face-to-face learning activities that are integrated in a "planned, pedagogically valuable way and where some of the face-to-face time is replaced by online activities [3]. According to Allen, Seaman, and Garrett a blended course has anywhere between 30 to 79% of online content delivery with the remaining content delivered in a non-web based method such as face-to-face instruction [4]. Just as there are many definitions of blended learning, there are many reasons why blended learning is becoming increasingly popular. Institutions of higher education are using blended instruction to improve pedagogy, increase access to and the flexibility of learning environments, and improve cost-effectiveness, but the most common reason is to improve pedagogical practices [1, 5]. Major reasons for faculty adoption of the blended technique are to increase student engagement and involvement in the learning process and to improve student learning [5; 6; 7; 8; 9]. Student-reported satisfaction with blended.

instruction has generally been very positive with convenience and controlling the pace of learning considered to be the major benefits of the blended approach [8; 9; 10].

One of the advantages of blended learning is that it can educate a wide audience at the same time. In addition to traditional education, online classes are organized with students, and independent education is used for students to study independently.

Blended learning also allows teachers to spend less time conducting whole classroom lessons and more time with students to help them solve individual concepts, skills, questions, or learning problems individually or in small groups will give. Or "translated instruction" is a form of blended learning. Blended learning can also allow schools to enroll more students more efficiently at a lower cost if the student is in school and higher education. As students are required to use digital and online technologies in a mixed learning environment, they will naturally gain more technological literacy and greater confidence using new technologies. Some proponents may also argue that the blended learning approach is more similar to modern workplaces, in that employees can work largely independently to achieve specific goals, only occasionally with their supervisors and can check with their mentors to give them updates or ask for help.

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In general, blended learning creates a lot of opportunities, which in many ways depends on the quality of designing and implementing a particular blended learning model. In traditional education, students are taught, and in blended learning - they are taught to read, to organize independent activities. In this case, students learn skills such as self-discipline, self-motivation, and organizational habits that are needed in adult life.

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